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Review Article

Therapeutic Properties of Acacia Arabica Extract in Traditional and Modern Medicine

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ABSTRACT

Acacia Arabica, commonly known as gum Arabic, has been utilized in traditional medicine systems across various cultures for its wide-ranging therapeutic benefits. In traditional medicine, this plant is renowned for its diuretic properties, gum for digestive health, and wound-healing properties. It has been used to treat gastrointestinal disorders, respiratory issues, and skin conditions. Modern scientific research has corroborated many of these many modern uses such as, herbal medicine and control release formulation highlighting its potential in contemporary therapeutic applications. The primary constituents include polysaccharides, particularly gum arabic, which is a complex mixture of glycoproteins and polysaccharides. Other notable compounds include flavonoids, tannins, saponins, and essential oils, all contributing to its therapeutic effects.. The extraction of bioactive compounds from Acacia Arabica typically involves several methods. Traditional extraction methods include boiling and solvent extraction using water or alcohol. Modern techniques often employ more advanced methods such as Soxhlet extraction, ultrasonic-assisted extraction, and supercritical fluid extraction to enhance yield and purity. These methods are designed to optimize the extraction of active components, ensuring that the therapeutic potential of the plant is maximized .In summary, Acacia Arabica holds significant promise in both traditional and modern medicine due to its diverse chemical profile and therapeutic properties. Ongoing research continues to validate and explore its efficacy, potentially leading to new therapeutic applications.

INTRODUCTION

The World Health Organization (WHO) has listed more than 21,000 plants, which are used for many medicinal purposes around the world that observed

that about 74% of 119 plant-derived pharmaceutical medicines are used in modern medicine. It also estimates that 4 billion people (80 percent of the world population) presently use

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herbal medicine for health care. Over hundreds of years, herbal medicines derived from medicinal plants minerals and organic matter is still about the of about 75–80% of the world's population for health Care marketed and gaining popularity developed and developing countries. In the last few years there is an exponential growth in the field of herbal medicine because of their natural origin, easy availability efficacy, safety and less side effects with efficientr which no modern medicine is available.⁽⁰¹⁾ Worldwide recognition as a multipurpose tree has been accorded to *Acacia nilotica* (L.) Wild. Ex Del, also known as babul, kikar, or Indian gum Arabic tree (National Academy of Sciences 1980). Because of its invasiveness, ability to spread, and negative effects on the environment and economy, it is considered one of the worst weeds in Australia. It is abundantly found in arid and semi-arid regions of the globe. Currently, wasteland makes up 20% of India's overall geographic area. Finding appropriate nitrogen-fixing plants is crucial since these types of lands typically lack nitrogen. *A. nilotica* may have a significant impact. It is a versatile legume that grows very quickly and can withstand droughts. It can also fix nitrogen biologically. Furthermore, it has a robust tap root structure (Tokay and Bisht 1992), a protracted growth season (more than 300 days) with four leaf flush maxima (Benewah et al 1992), and the ability to actively mine the soil column for moisture and nutrients. In addition to providing strong timber, high-quality fuel wood, and goat and sheep fodder, this species has a high potential for nitrogen fixation (Tokyo et al., 1994). It is also one of the quickly expanding wastelands species in India's agroforestry systems.⁽⁰²⁾ Since then, plants and plant extracts have been utilized medicinally and have become increasingly important in developing nations. They come from nature, are affordable, and work well. The herb *Acacia Nilotica* is commonly utilized in traditional medicine. Nearly

every part of them, including the root, bark, leaves, flowers, gums, and pods, is utilized in medicine. This herb possesses antibacterial, antiplasmodial, anticancer, antimutagenic, and antioxidant properties. It is used to treat piles, hepatitis C virus, burns, scalds, and cough, sore throat, diarrhea, dysentery, and tuberculosis. Several typical pharmacological applications for various sections of⁽⁰³⁾

2. Chemicle Constituents (Phytochemical)

Acacia species contains secondary metabolites including amines and alkaloids, cyanogen glycosides, cyclitols, fatty acids and seed oils, fluoroacetate, gums, nonprotein amino acids, terpenes (including essential oils, diterpenes, phytosterol and triterpene genins and saponins), hydrolyzable tannins flavonoids and condensed tannins. The plant is richer source of cysteine, methionine, threonine, lysine, tryptophan, Potassium, phosphorus, magnesium, iron and manganese. The plant chemical compounds like diester, pentacosane dioxin acid dihexadecyl ester and is alcohol, heptacosane 1, 2, 3-triol. Seeds: It contain high percentage of phenolic constituents consisting of m-digallic acid, gallic acid, protocatechuic and ellagic acids, leucocyanidin, mdigallic dimer 3,4,5,7-tetrahydroxy flavan-3-ol, oligomer 3,4,7- trihydroxy flavan 3,4-diol and 3,4,5,7- tetrahydroxy flavan-3-ol and (-) epicatechol. The mature seed is also a higher source of cystine, methionine, threonine, lysine, and tryptophan. It also contains crude protein, crude fiber, crude fat, carbohydrates, potassium, phosphorus, magnesium, iron, and manganese in high proportions. Fruit also has saponins and mucilage. Pods: It has condensed tannins, Gallic acid, and its Me-ester-n-digallic acid. Leaf: It has 12.4% crude protein, rutin, 6-8-bis-D-glucoside, and 8% digesting protein. Pods that have been seeded (50%), pods (5.4%), leaves (7.6%), bark (13.5%), and twigs (15.8%) have varying relative quantities of tannin (28). Bark: This material has

12–20% tannin content, along with terpenoids, saponins, glycosides, gallic acid, protocatechuic acid, pyrocatechol, phenol butane, (+)-catechin, (-) epigallocatechin-5, 7-digallate (29). Total phenolic content in its extract ranges from 9.2 to 16.5 g/100 g⁽³⁰⁾. Root: It has botulin, octacosanol, and Bsitosterol. Gum: It is composed of galacto araban which gives on hydrolysis L-arabinose, D-galactose, Lrhamn⁽⁰¹⁾

3. Different Techniques Involved In Phyto - Chemical Analysis

The many preliminary qualitative techniques are frequently employed to determine the chemical composition of the plant. We can utilize the Mayer, Hager, and Wagner tests to determine whether alkaloids are present. Phenolic substances and tannins: lead acetate test, magnesium and hydrochloric acid reduction, ferric chloride, gelatin test, alkaline reagent test, and so forth. Test for amino acids: Ninhydrin. Tests for carbohydrates: Benedict's and Molise's. Spot test and saponification test for fixed oils and fats. Glycosides: Borntrager's test and the legal test. Libermann-Burchard test: phytosterols. Proteins: Biuret and Million's tests. Foam test for saponins. Check for volatile oil and for gum and mucilage. Test for terpenoids: Salkowski's Shinoda and alkaline reagent tests for flavonoids. Heart-related)%⁽⁰³⁾ Glycosides: The killer kiliani test. Borntrager's assay for anthraquinones Comparable to qualitative and quantitative. Phytochemical analysis can be conducted by Optimum Performance Laminar Chromatography (OPLC), Gas Chromatography (GC), High Performance Thin Layer Chromatography (HPTLC), High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), and Gas Chromatography Mass Spectroscopy (GCMS) [03]. Moreover, phytochemical research frequently makes use of spectroscopic detection methods as UV, IR, MS, 13C-NMR, and 1H-NMR [03].

4. Phytochemicals Found In Different Plant Parts Of Acacia Nilotica And Their Medicinal Values

4.1. Bark

Phytochemical analysis of ethanol and petroleum ether extract of the stem bark of *Acacia nilotica* exposed that the plant contains terpenoids, tannins, alkaloids, saponins, glycosides. And the carbohydrates and anthraquinone were detected in ethanol extract by while the results described by Okoro S. O. et al. revealed that, the ethanolic extracts of *Acacia nilotica* possess sterols and tannins; no alkaloids, saponins or glycosides.⁽⁰³⁾ The outermost layer of the stem and roots of the woody plants is known as bark. Phytochemical screening of the bark of *A. nilotica* plant showed the presence of tannins, terpenoids, alkaloids, saponins, glycosides, carbohydrates and anthraquinone. Tannins are majorly present in the stem bark.⁽⁰⁴⁾

1 **Tannins:** *Acacia nilotica* bark is particularly rich in tannins, which are polyphenolic compounds known for their astringent properties and potential health benefits. Tannins have been studied for their antioxidant, antimicrobial, and anti-inflammatory activities.⁽⁰⁵⁾

2) **Saponins:** These compounds are known for their ability to form foams and their potential as natural detergents. Saponins have also shown various biological activities, including antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory effects.⁽⁰⁶⁾

3) **Alkaloids:** The bark contains various alkaloids, which are nitrogenous compounds with potential pharmacological effects, including analgesic and anti-inflammatory properties.⁽⁰⁷⁾

4) **Flavonoids:** These are a diverse group of phytonutrients with antioxidant properties. Flavonoids in *Acacia nilotica* bark contribute to its potential health benefits, including cardiovascular protection⁽⁰⁸⁾.

5) **Phenolic Compounds:** These compounds have antioxidant properties and may contribute to the bark's ability to combat oxidative stress. ⁽⁰⁹⁾

6) **Glycosides:** These compounds are known for their role in various biological activities and can contribute to the bark's therapeutic potential. ⁽¹⁰⁾

4.2. Roots

Lukman A. et al. determine the presence of saponins, flavonoids, terpenes, tannins, phenols, alkaloids, and anthraquinones. Okoro S. O. et al. conducted a screening study of the ethanolic extracts of the roots of *Acacia nilotica* and found the presence of sterols and tannins. The aqueous extract also contains tannins, saponins, flavonoids, phenols, sterols, and anthraquinones. ⁽⁰³⁾

A. nilotica roots are well-known for their ethno medicinal qualities. *A. Nilotic a's* aqueous root extract has anti plasmodial action against *Plasmodium berghei*. Polygalloyltannin, which was extracted from the plant's crude methanolic root extracts, showed notable efficacy against a mouse strain of *Plasmodium Bergheim* that is sensitive to chloroquine⁴⁵. *A. nilotica's* aqueous root preparations contain alkaloids and flavonoids that have strong antipyretic and analgesic properties ^(04.)

1) **Tannins:** *Acacia nilotica* roots are rich in tannins, which are known for their astringent and antimicrobial properties. Tannins play a role in the plant's medicinal efficacy. ⁽¹¹⁾

2) **Saponins:** These compounds exhibit a range of biological activities, including antimicrobial and immunomodulatory effects. ⁽¹²⁾

3) **Flavonoids:** These polyphenolic compounds have antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial properties. ⁽¹³⁾

4) **Alkaloids:** Nitrogenous compounds with various biological activities, including potential therapeutic effects. ⁽¹⁴⁾

5) **Phenolic Compounds:** These compounds have antioxidant properties and contribute to the plant's therapeutic potential. ⁽¹⁵⁾

6) **Glycosides:** These compounds, where a sugar is bound to another functional group, are also present in the roots and contribute to the plant's medicinal properties. ⁽¹⁶⁾

4.3. Pods

To test for the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, tannin, cardiac glycoside, sterol, and carbohydrates, Sabah E. et al. used a new solvent. They made use of petroleum ether extracts, water, and ethanol. Alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, saponins, and carbohydrates were all found in positive amounts in water and ethanol extracts. Sterol was found in ethanol and petroleum ether extracts, but neither saponins nor carbohydrates were found in petroleum ether. Oladosu P. et al. also used an aqueous methanol extract to identify alkaloids, saponins, tannins, and carbohydrates. ⁽⁰³⁾

A. nilotica produces bitter, dry pods with a fragrant smell as its fruits. Their mucilage, tannins, and saponins are abundant³⁹. Their phytochemical investigations revealed that the pods of the *A. nilotica* plant included proteins, carbohydrates, phenols, tannins, saponins, starch, flavonoids, and steroids⁶³. The tannin content of these pods ranges from 12–19%, and in deseeded pods, it can reach 19–27%. Dry pods also contain 15.8% crude proteins². *Acacia* fruits are well-known for their therapeutic properties. They have been used to treat a variety of illnesses since ancient times. ⁽⁰⁴⁾

1) **Tannins:** Known for its astringent, antibacterial, and anti-inflammatory qualities, the pods contain tannins. ⁽¹⁷⁾

2) **Flavonoids:** These substances have antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant properties. ⁽¹⁸⁾

3) **Saponins:** It has been reported that the pods' saponins may have antifungal, antibacterial, and hypoglycemic properties. ⁽¹⁹⁾

4) Phenolic Compounds: Known for its antioxidant qualities, these compounds add to the pods' total therapeutic worth⁽²⁰⁾.

5) Glycosides: These substances are present in the pods and are involved in a variety of biological processes. They are sugars attached to other chemical groups⁽²¹⁾

6) Alkaloids: The pods contain alkaloids, which have a variety of biological properties, such as antibacterial and anti-inflammatory properties. Effects⁽²²⁾

4.4. Leaves

Through phytochemical screening of ethanolic extracts, tannins, alkaloids, and sterols were found in *Acacia nilotica* leaves; glycosides, saponins, resins, and flavonoids were not found. Additionally, alkaloids, saponins, cardiac glycosides, tannins, and flavonoids were shown by Mrityunjoy Das ET al. The leaves of the tamarind tree and the *Acacia* plant exhibit similarities. They have a lot of proteins and tannins. Condensed tannin nins, which are used as preservatives and in medicine to cure a variety of illnesses, have historically been discovered in the leaves of numerous *Acacia* species²⁶. The leaves' decoction has an astringent quality that helps with digestive issues, eye conditions, bronchitis treatment, and fracture healing.⁽⁰³⁾

The phytochemicals found in *A. nilotica* leaf extracts, such as saponins, glycosides, hydrolysable tannins, triterpenoid, flavonoids, phenol, alkaloids, and volatile oils, are highly beneficial in treating a wide range of medical conditions⁷⁴. These extracts have several uses, including strengthening vision and curing eye problems, as well as acting as an astringent to treat acute leucorrhoea, gonorrhoea, and as a liver and brain tonic⁵⁸.⁽⁰⁴⁾ According to Vijayasanthi et al., alkaloids found in the leaf extract have antimicrobial activity against *Candida albicans*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Aspergillus Niger*, *Escherichia coli*, *Micrococcus luteus*, *Pseudomonas*

aeruginosa, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Staphylococcus epidermidis*.⁽⁰⁴⁾

1) Tannins: These polyphenolic substances are well-known for having antibacterial and antioxidant qualities.⁽²³⁾

2) Flavonoids: These are substances with anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties, such as kaempferol and quercetin. Kharb⁽²⁴⁾

3) Saponins: Studies have demonstrated the antibacterial and immunomodulatory effects of these glycosides.⁽²⁵⁾

4) Alkaloids: Compounds that contain nitrogen and have a range of biological functions, including the ability to reduce inflammation. Saha⁽²⁶⁾

5) Phenolic Acids: These include ferulic acid and caffeic acid, which are known for their strong antioxidant qualities. suxen⁽²⁷⁾

4.5. Flower

Catechins, which are phenolic compounds, were found in flowers^[03]. *A. nilotica* flowers have a yellow or golden-yellow tint. Flowers were shown to be rich in tannins, terpenoids, flavonoids, steroids, and saponins through phytochemical screening. Many bioactive substances, such as catechin, catechin 7-O-galate, gallic acid, naringenin 7-O- β -glucopyranoside, quercetin 3-O- β -glucoside (2 $\rightarrow$ 1) glucopyranoside, chalconaringenin 4'-O- β -glucopyranoside, naringenin, eanic acid, kaempferol-3-glucoside, isoquercetin, leucocyanidin(2), etc. are extracted and identified from the flowers of *A. nilotica*.⁽⁰⁴⁾

When evaluated in vitro for DPPH and deoxyribose degradation assays, kaempferol, which was extracted from the methanol extract of flowers, demonstrated strong dose-dependent antioxidant activity⁷³. The flowers of *A. nilotica* are effective in tonic preparations for the treatment of dysentery and diarrhea because they have a variety of biological and pharmacological qualities. The flowers of *A. nilotica* are applied in traditional medical systems to treat gastrointestinal

ailments and to lower body temperature. They are also beneficial as a cure for insanity⁶⁴.⁽⁰⁴⁾

1) **Flavonoids:** These compounds, such as quercetin and kaempferol, are noted for their antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and anticancer activities.⁽²⁸⁾

2) **Saponins:** Glycosidic compounds known for their antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and immune-boosting properties.⁽²⁹⁾

3) **Tannins:** Polyphenolic compounds with antioxidant and antimicrobial effects.⁽³⁰⁾

4) **Phenolic Compounds:** Such as gallic acid and ellagic acid, which have significant antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties.⁽³¹⁾

5) **Essential Oils:** The flowers contain essential oils with potential antimicrobial and aromatic properties. Gupta⁽³²⁾

4.6 Seeds:

The plant's seeds have a spherical shape and are consistently gray at the base. They are beneficial for feeding animals since they are rich in proteins and fatty acids from several lipid classes⁸⁶. Mature seeds have extremely high amounts of iron, phosphorus, potassium, manganese, magnesium, crude fiber, crude protein, and crude fat¹. A variety of phenolic chemicals, found in larger quantities in seeds, include gallic acid, ellagic acid, m-digallic acid, m-galic dimer, leucocyanidine, and 3,4,7-tetrahydroxy flavones. As far as biochemistry is concerned, seeds are composed of 2.7% crude fiber, 26.4% crude protein, calcium, phosphorus, iron, niacin, ascorbic acid, and thiamine. The essential amino acids histidine, lysine, methionine, cystine, phenylalanine, tyrosine, leucine, isoleucine, valine, and threonine are present in the crude protein portion of the seeds.⁽⁰⁴⁾

Certain bacteria that produce β -lactamase, such as *Escherichia coli*, *Proteus vulgaris*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Staphylococcus aureus*, are inhibited in their growth by the ethanolic seed-pod extract. A.

nilotica crude seed oil preparations have antifungal properties against *Aspergillus niger*⁷⁷ and *Candida albicans*.⁽⁰⁴⁾

1) **Tannins:** These polyphenolic substances have antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant qualities.⁽³³⁾

2) **Flavonoids:** These are substances with anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties, such as rutin quercetin.⁽³⁴⁾

3) **Saponins:** Research has indicated that these glycosidic molecules possess antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, and immunomodulatory properties.⁽³⁵⁾

4) **Alkaloids:** Compounds that contain nitrogen and may have anti-inflammatory and analgesic properties.⁽³⁶⁾

5) **Phenolic Compounds:** These include ellagic and gallic acids, which are well-known for their anticancer and antioxidant qualities.⁽³⁷⁾

6) **Essential Oils:** The seeds have essential oils that may have medicinal and antibacterial effects.⁽³⁸⁾

4.7) Gum exudate:

Indian gum Arabic, the gum secreted by *A. nilotica*, is being investigated extensively for its potential uses in food, medicine, and industry²⁹. Gummy exudate can be extracted from a tree's injured bark between March and May. The amount of tannin in it determines how dark reddish-brown or mild yellowish-brown it is. Numerous pharmacological and therapeutic uses can be derived from phytochemicals that were extracted from arabic gum.⁽⁰⁴⁾ Sugars like L-arabinose, L-rhamnose, D-galactose, and four aldobiouronic acids, specifically 6-O-(β -D-glucopyranosyluronic acid), are the main sugars found in arabic gum.-(β -D-glucose, 6-O-methyl- β -D-glucosyluronic acid)-(α -D-glucopyranosyluronic acid)-(D-galactose, 4-O-)-4-O-(4-O-methyl- α -D-glucopyranosyluronic acid) and -D-galactose-D-galactose 10. Leucocyanidin, mdigallic acid, gallic acid, methyl and ethyl esters,

protocatechuic and ellagic acids, oligomer 3,4,7-trihydroxyflavan 3,4-diol and 3,4,5,7-tetrahydroxyflavan-3-ol, and (-) epicatechol⁶⁵ are among the phenolic constituents that make up a significant portion of the gum. Tannic acid, methylsalicylate⁴⁸, and cresol, an antibacterial, are other ingredients in gum. ⁽⁰⁴⁾ Regarding the therapeutic properties of *A. nilotica* gum exudate, traditional medical systems use it as an astringent, emollient, and liver tonic⁷. In cases of sexual impairment, gum fried in ghee can be used as an aphrodisiac and nutritional tonic⁵⁸. The gum helps treat lung issues and is expectorant, antipyretic, and antiasthmatic ⁽⁰⁴⁾

1) Glycosides: Gum acacia has a number of glycosides, some of which have antibacterial and antioxidant qualities. ⁽³⁹⁾

2) Tannins: The gum's antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant qualities are facilitated by these polyphenolic chemicals. ⁽⁴⁰⁾

3) Phenolic Compounds: These consist of substances with potent anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties, such as gallic and ellagic acids. ⁽⁴¹⁾

4) Saponins: Although they are present in smaller quantities, gum acacia contains saponins, which support the gum's immune system and antibacterial qualities. Dear ⁽⁴²⁾

5) Polysaccharides: The main component of gum is polysaccharides, which are advantageous due to their mucilage and possible prebiotic properties. ⁽⁴³⁾

Showing Different Image Of Acacia Nilotica

Fig. 1. A twig of *A. nilotica* showing flowers

Fig. 2. Pods of *A. nilotica*

Fig 3 Bark of Acacia Nilotica

Fig 4 seeds of Acacia Nilotica

2. Material and Method of Extraction of Acacia Arebica

The bark of *A. arabica* that was gathered from Bhopal was recognized and verified by the Vindhya Herbals House of the Minor Forest Produce Processing & Research Center (MFP – PARC). Three distinct batches of powdered *A. arabica* bark that had been dried and ground were weighed, to which methanol, ethyl acetate, and a methanol-water combination were added in that order. Three distinct techniques—maceration,

soxhlet, and microwave—were used to carry out the extraction process. Each solution was separated and allowed to evaporate until the solvent was completely gone. After obtaining the crude extracts, they were weighed, the yield percentage was calculated, and they were kept in airtight vials at 10°C for further use⁽⁴⁴⁾

2.1 Maceration

In maceration, coarsely powdered crude bark was placed in a conical flask with 100ml solvent and allowed to stand at room temperature for a period of at least 24 hours With frequent agitation... The mixture was then strained and solvent evaporated at room Temperature⁽⁴⁴⁾

2.2 Soxhlet Extraction

For Soxhlet extraction, 4:1 ratio of solvent and sample of the bark was placed in the column plugged with glass wool. The procedure was performed in a model of six soxhlet extractor for 24-36 hours using methanol, Mixture. Solvent was dried at room temperature and crude extract screened for phytochemicals⁽⁴⁴⁾

2.3 Microwave Assisted Extraction

Microwave assisted extraction of bark was performed in LG Intellowave, 800W Microwave. The microwave power was reduced and sample irradiated for 3- 4 min. The extracts were separated from the plant material by filtration using Whatmann No.1 Filter paper. The filtered solvent was subsequently evaporated and crude extract was analysed For phytochemicals⁽⁴⁴⁾

2.4 Qualitative Phytochemical Analysis

2.4.1 Test for alkaloids

2.4.1.1 Hager's test: 1 ml of Hager's reagent solution was added to 2ml of extract, yellow Precipitate confirms the presence of alkaloids.⁽⁴⁴⁾

2.4.2 Test for Proteins

2.4.2.1 million tests: 3-4 drops of extract was added to 0.5ml of distilled water and few Drops of million's reagent confirms proteins⁽⁴⁴⁾

2.4.2.2 Biuret test: 1ml of extract added to 1drop of copper sulphate, 0.5ml ethanol and 6-7 pellets of potassium hydroxide, pink color confirms proteins⁽⁴⁴⁾

2.4.2.3 Ninhydrin test: 1ml of extract added to 2 drops of ninhydrin solution gives purple Color solution thereby confirming proteins⁽⁴⁴⁾

2.4.3 Test for carbohydrates

2.4.3.1 Molisch test: 0.5 ml of extract in 0.5 ml of distilled water was mixed with 2 drops of Molisch reagent. Test tubes were filled with concentrated sulfuric acid; the creation of a violet ring at the intersection indicates the presence of carbohydrates.⁽⁴⁴⁾

2.4.3.2 Fehling's test: Place 1 milliliter each of Fehling solutions A and B in a test tube, bring to a boil, and then add 0.5 milliliter of extract. The presence of red precipitate indicates the presence of carbohydrates⁽⁴⁴⁾

2.4.4 Tests for Glycosides

0.5ml of extract was added to 3-4drops of HCl and heated for 5minutes. The mixture Was divided in two parts A and B.⁽⁴⁴⁾

2.4.4.1 Borntrager's test: To part a, added 2ml of chloroform followed by addition of Ammonia solution along the sides of test tube, pink color confirms glycosides⁽⁴⁴⁾

2.4.4.2 Legal's test: To part B, added 0.5ml of pyridine and 0.5ml sodium Nitroprusside, and NaOH in excess, pink color indicates glycosides⁽⁴⁴⁾

2.4.5 Test for phenolic compound

Ferric chloride test: To 0.5ml extract added 2ml of distilled water and few drops of neutral ferric chloride, dark green color confirms phenols.⁽⁴⁴⁾

2.4.6 Tests for Flavonoids

2.4.6.1 Lead acetate test: To 0.5ml extract, added 0.5ml distilled water and 1ml lead Acetate. Bulky white precipitate appeared⁽⁴⁴⁾

2.4.6.2 Shinoda Test: Pieces of magnesium ribbon and concentrated HCl were mixed

With extract. Appearance of pink color showed the presence of flavonoid⁽⁴⁴⁾

2.4.6.3 Alkaline Reagent Test: To 0.5ml of extract in distilled water, 10% ammonium Hydroxide was added drop wise; yellow fluorescence showed the presence of Flavonoids⁽⁴⁴⁾.

2.4.7 Test for phytosterols

2.4.7.1 Test for Tannins: 0.5ml extract was added to the basic lead acetate. White Precipitate showed the presence of tannins⁽⁴⁴⁾

2.4.7.2 Test for Saponins: 0.5ml of extract was mixed with 5-6ml of distilled water the Foam appearance showed the presence of saponins.⁽⁴⁴⁾

2.5 Quantitative Phytochemical Analysis

2.5.1 Calculating the Whole Phenolic Content

Using the Folin-Ciocalteu Reagent, the total phenolic content of the methanol extracts from all three techniques was determined. The result was represented as milligrams of gallic acid equivalent per gram of sample. At 765 nm, absorbance was measured.⁽⁴⁴⁾

2.5.2 Calculating the Total Content of Flavonoids

Using the Rutin/quercetin method, the total flavonoid content of the methanol extract from three separate procedures was determined. The results were represented as mg equivalent of Rutin per gm. of dry sample. At 510 nm, absorbance was measured.⁽⁴⁴⁾

2.5.3 Calculating the Tannin Content in Total the Folin-Ciocalteu method was used to calculate the total tannin content, which was then reported in mg of GAE/g of extract. At 725 nm, absorbance was measured.⁽⁴⁴⁾

2.6 Antioxidant Activity using the DPPH Method of Assay

Antioxidant activity was assessed in a methanol extract of Acacia bark made using a microwave-assisted extraction method. Various test sample concentrations ranging from 20 to 100 µg/ml were generated. For 10 minutes, the mixture was

incubated in the dark at room temperature with 2 milliliters of the test sample added to 1 milliliter of DPPH solution. With a blank (methanol) in place, the absorbance was measured at 515 nm using a Systronic 2202 double beam UV-Vis spectrophotometer. The percentage inhibition was computed. Using following formula: % Inhibition = $[(AC\ 515\ nm - AS\ 515\ nm) / AC\ 515\ nm] \times 100$ the absorbance of the sample is AS, whereas the absorbance of the control is AC. A line of regression was used to compute the IC50 value and plot the percentage of inhibition on a curve.⁽⁴⁴⁾

Traditional Uses of Acacia Arabica

1. Gum for Digestive Health

1. Gum for Digestive Health Uses: Historically, Acacia arabica gum has been utilized as a treatment for digestive problems such as dysentery and diarrhea. The mucilaginous qualities of the gum aid in protecting and calming the gastrointestinal system. Gum is said to have a demulcent effect, which means it calms and shields mucous membranes. This characteristic helps alleviate inflammation or irritation of the mucous membranes.⁽⁴⁵⁾

2. **Use in Wound Healing:** Traditionally, wounds and ulcers have been treated using acacia arabica gum. Its use promotes infection prevention and speeds up wound healing. The gum is a helpful topical agent because of its protecting and sticky properties. It creates a barrier over wounds to help promote quicker healing and prevent infection.⁽⁴⁶⁾

3. Respiratory Health

Application: In traditional medicine, Acacia arabica gum is used to treat coughs, colds, and other respiratory ailments. The gum is often used in syrups and lozenges. The mucilaginous nature of the gum helps in soothing the throat and respiratory tract, reducing irritation and cough. Its expectorant properties help in clearing mucus from the airways.⁽⁴⁷⁾

4. Skin Care

Application: Acacia arabica gum has been used traditionally in skin care for its moisturizing and emollient properties. It is applied to treat dry skin conditions and minor skin irritations. The gum's ability to form a film over the skin helps in retaining moisture and providing a barrier against environmental factors. It is used in various traditional skin care remedies and cosmetics.⁽⁴⁸⁾

5. Diuretic Properties

Application: Acacia arabica gum is used as a diuretic in certain traditional practices to increase urine flow and treat UTIs. The gum's modest diuretic action aids in the management of illnesses such as urinary tract infections and the removal of toxins. It also aids in the urinary system's reduction of irritation.⁽⁴⁹⁾

6. As a Vehicle in Herbal Formulations:

Historically, powdered and liquid extracts containing herbs have been formulated using gum arabic as a foundation or vehicle. Herbal powders are easier to combine and maintain together because of the gum's inherent adhesive qualities. Moreover, it stabilizes herbal extracts, guaranteeing that the active components are evenly dispersed and efficient.⁽⁵⁰⁾

Modern Uses of Acacia Arabica

1. Herbal Extract Stabilization

Application: Liquid herbal extracts are stabilized through the application of Acacia arabica gum in herbal medicine technology. Over time, the natural gum in it creates a durable gel-like matrix that supports the preservation of the potency and integrity of the herbal extracts. Gum arabic serves as a stabilizing agent by keeping the active substances well distributed and preventing component separation. This is especially helpful in keeping delicate herbal ingredients from degrading.⁽⁵¹⁾

2. Formulations with Controlled Release

Application: Controlled release medication delivery devices make use of Acacia arabica gum. It is employed in the production of matrices that

enhance therapeutic results by allowing the slow release of herbal active components. Herbal ingredients can be encapsulated by the gum in a matrix that resembles gel, enabling regulated and prolonged release. This aids in lowering the frequency of dosage and improving patient compliance.⁽⁵²⁾

3. Tablet and Capsule Formulations

Application: Gum arabic is utilized as a binder and disintegrant in the formulation of herbal tablets and capsules. It ensures that the tablets remain intact during storage but disintegrate properly in the digestive tract to release active ingredients. As a binder, gum arabic helps in binding the herbal powder into a solid form. As a disintegrant, it aids in breaking the tablet down in the gastrointestinal tract, facilitating the release and absorption of herbal ingredients.⁽⁵³⁾

4. Capsule Coatings

Application: Acacia arabica gum is used as a film-forming agent in the coating of herbal capsules. This coating helps in controlling the release rate of the herbal contents and protects the capsules from environmental factors. The gum forms a protective film around the capsule, which can be tailored to dissolve at specific rates, enhancing the controlled release of herbal substances.⁽⁵⁴⁾

5. Emulsification in Herbal Preparations

Application: Gum arabic is used as an emulsifier in herbal preparations, particularly in oil-in-water emulsions. This helps in stabilizing the mixture of oil and water phases, which is crucial for the uniform distribution of herbal ingredients.

: The emulsifying properties of gum arabic ensure that herbal oils are evenly distributed in aqueous solutions, which improves the stability and efficacy of liquid herbal formulations.⁽⁵⁵⁾

6. Mucoadhesive Drug Delivery Systems

Application: Gum arabic is used in mucoadhesive drug delivery systems for oral and buccal administration of herbal drugs. Its adhesive properties help in retaining the drug at the mucosal

site for an extended period. The mucoadhesive nature of gum arabic enhances the contact time of herbal drugs with mucosal surfaces, leading to better absorption and efficacy. *Acacia arabica*, particularly its gum, has several modern health-related applications in herbal drug technology. These uses capitalize on the gum's unique properties and its traditional benef⁽⁵⁶⁾

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